

THE USAGE AND SYNTACTIC FUNCTIONS OF GERUND

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ANNOTATSIYA.

Mazkur maqolada nopredikativ fe`l shakllaridan biri hisoblangan gerundiy haqida ma`lumot berilgan, uning ba`zi ingliz va o`zbek yozuvchilarining asarlarida qo`llanilishi, qanday sintaktik vazifalarda kelishi yoritilgan. Shuningdek nopredikativ fe`l shakllarining qo`llanilishi bilan bog`liq qator ingliz va o`zbek tillaridagi ilmiy manbalar, darslik, qo`llanmalar asosida gerundiy grammatik-sintaktik nuqtai nazaridan chog`ishtirma tahlil natijalari keltirilgan.

Kalit so`zlar: gerundiy, nopredikativ fe`l shakllari, chog`ishtirma tahlil.

ANNOTATION.

This article provides information about the gerund, one of the non-predicative verb forms, its usage and syntactic functions in the works of some English and Uzbek writers,. Also, the results of comparative analysis from the grammatical and syntactic point of view of the gerund on the basis of a number of scientific sources, textbooks, manuals in English and Uzbek languages related to the use of non-predicative verb forms.

Keywords: gerund, non-predicate verb forms, comparative analysis

In language learning, one of the language rules that has important role in communication is gerund. According to Wliting (1983:32), gerund has a force of a noun if the gerund has a substantive feature such as having an article in front of it and having a plural noun. When a gerund has a force of noun, it has substantive meaning. Substantive is a word that can function as a gerund, an infinitive, and a noun. The gerund has a force a verb if the gerund has a verbal feature such as having its own object and having change in the perfect and the passive. When a gerund becomes a hybrid because it has a noun form but it has a verbal meaning. In this study, the writer focuses on the -ing form as gerund. According to Swan (1995:27), gerund is a verbal that ends in -ing and functions as a noun. It is one of the oddest constructions in the English language, because it nominalizes morpheme, turning a verb into a noun by adding -ing form to the end of the verb. At the same time, there is also continuous tense that adds -ing form to the end of the verb. For those who begins learn English can easily become confused by this -ing form that can become noun and also verb at the same sentence, such as: smoking addiction has been killing millions of population over the last decade. As the continuous tense, the rule is clear, the verb with -ing form is placed after the subject. The analysis is focused on gerunds of subject, direct object, subject complement, and object of preposition.

Gerund isa word derived from a verb base which functions as or like a noun. George (1990:268) says that gerund is the - ing form of the verb used as a noun, gerund has the same form as the present participle. However, it functions differently in the sentence, it is always can function in any noun position. Harper (2006:234) mentions that a gerund is a kind of verbal noun. It behaves as a verb within a clause (so that, for example, it may be modified by an adverb or have an object), but the clause as a whole (sometimes consisting only of one

word, the gerund) acts as a noun within the larger sentence. Generally, gerund can occupy some positions in a sentence that a noun ordinarily would, which are: subject, direct object, subject complement, and object of preposition.

According to Harper (2006:234), the subject of a gerund usually denotes a live being, but sometimes it designates a lifeless thing or an abstract idea. In the majority of gerund phrases, especially those functions as objects of verbs or preposition, the “subject” is either understood or is found in another part of the sentence.

Harper (2006:234) also mentions that certain verbs in English are followed by verbals, either gerunds or infinitives, which are considered as the objects of these verbs. Most of these verbs denote mental activity or indirect speech and therefore require subjects that refer to human beings. Other have little semantic content outside of indicating aspect, the beginning, duration, end or repetition of an action; these verbs may or may not be used with subjects denoting persons. There is less agreement that a verbal following one of these aspects, denoting verbs is its objects; actually, there is some justification for considering a verb that expresses aspect as a quays, auxiliary rather than as a verb that takes an object.

Harper (2006:234) says that the form of an object in a gerund phrase may depend on what precedes the gerund. If the subject introduces the gerund, the object of the gerund is containing an of phrase.

Finally, Harper (2006:234) states that any verbs used as the object in a prepositional phrase takes the form of a gerund. Most gerund phrases after prepositions are subjectless, especially those in adverbial prepositional phrases.

A number of studies has been conducted to find out the importance of gerund. Damayanti (2009) has conducted a research about “An error Analysis on the Use of Gerunds and Infinitives: A Case Study on the Second Year Students Faculty of Letters, Gunadarma University”. In her research, she says that even though gerunds and infinitives have been offered to the students at semester four, it is still difficult for them to really understand the language. Consequently, in fact they still make many errors. This literature finds out the percentages of errors made by the second year students in understanding gerund and infinitive and discuss how those errors occur. The population of the study is the second year students of Faculty of Letters, Gunadarma University. The result of the analysis shows that the students have understood fairly on the study of gerunds and infinitives. Most of the students still find difficulties in understanding which verbs preceding gerund. Since the ability of the students in understanding gerund and infinitive is still below the requirement of a good grammar, the learning process of this material should be improved. Next, Duffley (2003) has conducted a research about: “The Gerund and the to-Infinitive as Subject”. In his research, he analyzes the corpus-based study in order to show that the distinction between the gerund and the infinitive. Finally, Rahmawati (2016) has conducted a research about: “An Analysis of Gerund and To Infinitive in The Articles of The Jakarta Post”. In her research, she analyzes the kinds of gerund and to infinitive in the sports articles of the Jakarta Post. The problems that should be answered in this research is the kinds of gerund and to infinitive that most frequently found in the articles of the Jakarta Post. The subject of the research are the articles of the Jakarta Post, while the object of the research is the kinds gerund and to infinitive that are used in the articles of the Jakarta Post. Distributional method is a method of analysis data that the object of analysis is the part of language itself, as opposed with referential method that relates the

object to the outside of language element. The object in distributional method is always the part or the element from the observed language, such as word (negation, preposition, adverb), syntactic function (subject, object, predicate), clause, word syllable, punctuation, and another (Sudaryanto, 1993: 15-16). It is the method of linguistic research in which the classification of linguistic units and the study of their features are carried out on the basis of the distribution of the units in question in the spoken chain, that is language units in question itself. The data which have been collected are analyzed as follows:

1. The use of Gerund.
2. Classified the Gerund.
3. Draw the conclusions.

Gerund as Subject

In this gerund, it is placed as the subject of sentence followed by the main verb. The formula can be seen in the following: Subject + Main Verb + Complement.

Gerund as Direct Object

In this gerund, it is placed at the object after the main verb, this gerund replaced the object of sentence. The formula can be seen in the following: Subject + Main Verb + Gerund.

Gerund as Subject Complement

In this gerund, it is placed as the complement after to be, it is not classified as continuous tense verb because the meaning of word is not a verb, but an activity of noun. The formula can be seen in the following: Subject + To be + Gerund. **Gerund as Object of Preposition**

In this gerund, it is placed as the object of sentence after the preposition. The formula can be seen in the following: Subject + Main Verb + Preposition + Gerund.

After analyzing the data, the researcher found that the four types of gerund, which are subject, direct object, subject complement, and object of preposition.

Due to the research problems, we may notice gerund is used with the higher percentage of gerund as the object of preposition. After drawing a conclusion within the data analysis, we find some points that hopefully should be covered by the next researchers. It is suggested that the students must be understood about gerunds and also the function of gerunds very well. For English students especially the beginners, it is important to be able in making sentences by understanding the usage of gerund first. Then, the writer also wishes this thesis can be useful to enrich knowledge about the usage and the function of gerund in English sentences and the students can get much information about gerunds from this writing and also apply it in English language.

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